

Testing and validation framework

Sustainability sheet

A framework for testing and validating ExPaNDs services against reference data sets. The process is demonstrated for the case of Jupyter notebook type services. This framework provides a path for delivering **analysis software as a service on shared infrastructure**, included but not limited to the EOSC and **shared HPC resources**.

	<p>Target audiences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific software developers - Software engineers 	<p>Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide a functional testing framework for software development teams - Make sure data analysis services are working correctly with heterogeneous compute infrastructures - Ensure long term reliability and sustainability of data analysis services - Ensure repeatability of scientific results
	<p>Accessibility</p> <p>The code repositories are publicly available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - jnbv (1): python module for testing Jupyter kernel and Jupyter notebooks against each other - Jupyter-notebook-validation (2): repository using jnbv for automated validation of production-ready Jupyter kernels as well as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the associated docker images (3) - the code used to produce them (4) - the HPC setup (5) used <p>Feedback mechanism</p> <p>GitLab issue tracking in the appropriate repository (9)</p>	<p>Documentation</p> <p>Methodology (6)</p> <p>Licence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC BY 4.0 (7) for documentation - BSD 2-Clause "Simplified" Licence (8) for code
	<p>Competitors</p> <p>Software Quality as a service from EOSC-Synergy (10)</p> <p>Technology readiness</p> <p>Pilot: in use at MAX IV, tested by other facilities (incl. ESRF) and could be easily configured to work in other infrastructures</p> <p>EOSC integration status</p> <p>Not onboarded</p>	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857641.

Plans and conditions for long-term sustainability

- MAX IV will maintain the framework for its own scientists
- It will continue to be hosted in [MAX IV's GitLab](#) (9)

Exploitability potential

- ExPaNDs and PaNOSC facilities can reuse the framework for their own jupyter notebook-type services
- The testing framework could be deployed as part of a CI/CD pipeline, e.g. in the frame of [LEAPS-INNOV WP7 on data compression](#) (11)
- There may be interest within national projects; e.g the [DAPHNE4NFDI project](#) (12) has a validation task for data and software reuse
- PaN could be a use case in a follow-up project to EOSC-Synergy
- The testing framework could be integrated within a future PaN container registry developed e.g. in the frame of OSCARS

Conditions to increase exploitability

- Extend the framework to non-jupyter based analysis services
- Add support for additional analysis workflows
- Allow users to upload their own analysis software, turning the framework into a “Testing as a Service” service
- Support integration with beamline data handling, allowing the framework to support near-real-time analysis

Links

- (1) <https://gitlab.com/MAXIV-SCISW/JUPYTERHUB/jnbv>
- (2) <https://gitlab.com/MAXIV-SCISW/JUPYTERHUB/jupyter-notebook-validation>
- (3) https://gitlab.com/MAXIV-SCISW/JUPYTERHUB/jupyter-docker-stacks/container_registry
- (4) <https://gitlab.com/MAXIV-SCISW/JUPYTERHUB/jupyter-docker-stacks>
- (5) <https://gitlab.com/MAXIV-SCISW/JUPYTERHUB/jupyterhub-hpc>
- (6) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5718671>
- (7) <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
- (8) <https://gitlab.com/MAXIV-SCISW/JUPYTERHUB/jupyter-notebook-validation/-/blob/master/LICENSE>
- (9) <https://gitlab.com/MAXIV-SCISW/JUPYTERHUB>
- (10) <https://sqaaas.eosc-synergy.eu/#/>
- (11) <https://www.leaps-innov.eu/wp-7>
- (12) <https://www.daphne4nfdi.de/english/index.php>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857641.